

Objective 3: Collectively discuss what is working, challenges, and how they can be addressed

To accomplish this objective, we conducted a value proposition activity on the second day of the workshop to capture the different jobs necessary “to support open and FAIR data sharing”, what would be gained by moving forward, and the likely pains (or challenges) that would likely be encountered. This activity helped us all to see that we share the same pains and gains and working together would be a significant benefit.

The intent is to share this content more broadly and consider how to address the challenges and take advantage of the value statements (“gains”) that will motivate the community. The comments are grouped by the roles: reviewers, editors, societies, publishers.

Reviewers – Supporting Data Sharing

- 1) Jobs
 - a) Review the data citation and availability statement for accuracy
 - b) Assess the science described in the paper using the data
 - c) Assess quality of research publications
- 2) Gains
 - a) Provides **credit** for datasets as a valuable product of research
 - b) Makes it easier to **validate assertions** made in the paper
 - c) Makes it possible for the **community to identify and evolve best data practices**
 - d) Demonstrate **leadership** of change in science best practices
 - e) Encourage more “eyes” to verify **data are appropriately shared**
- 3) Pains
 - a) There seems to be a continual learning curve
 - b) Currently there is little or no expertise among reviewers
 - c) The new activities take time
 - d) There are limited or “no” automated what to validate availability statements and data citations
 - e) This adds to scope creep on the reviewer’s job by including assessing data FAIR-ness as part of other reviewer responsibilities for the manuscript
 - f) There is not enough time to be as careful as is needed

Editors – Supporting Data Sharing

- 1) Jobs
 - a) Enforces best practices for data sharing
 - b) Coordinates the different roles necessary e.g. peer review, staff, repositories, etc
- 2) Gains
 - a) Improves the **quality** of publications
- 3) Pains
 - a) The difficulty of changing the existing culture of “data available by request”, or data “dumped” in the supplementary information

Societies – Supporting Data Sharing

- 1) Jobs
 - a) Support community building
 - b) Track/measure shifts in data sharing habits of members
 - c) Connect to data experts within memberships
 - d) Confirm data was deposited (may involve reviewing and curating)
 - e) Change award structures to include criteria for data management and data sharing
 - f) Recognize regularly through communication channels members with good data sharing stories
 - g) Amplify data community recommendations
 - h) Create standards, platforms, mechanisms, etc.
 - i) Educate on data sharing for members
 - j) Elevate importance of data management/sharing – champion/lobby/advocate/promote across member sections
 - k) Create and/or connect researchers to resources and training
 - l) Provide training, training, training
- 2) Gains
 - a) Develop **consistency** with society missions to advance science
 - b) Strengthen **reputation** (and trust)
 - c) Improve the **soundness** of science
 - d) Provide **value** for market
 - e) Elevate **society as a leader** in data sharing
 - f) Support **meta-science** and learn more about the discipline
 - g) Change **culture** around data sharing
 - h) Respond to **public** expectations/needs and funder mandates
- 3) Pains
 - a) Establish convincing governance of value
 - b) Takes away time from other projects
 - c) Education/awareness still needed for platforms (e.g. Wiley) that don't understand what is necessary to add value to science through data sharing
 - d) Need to develop more experienced/skilled staff
 - e) Value not perceived by members
 - f) Steep challenge with culture change among members – this is the way we have always done it
 - g) Must stimulate/incentivize members to adopt new data stewardship and data sharing behaviors
 - h) Results in likely reduction in revenue due to increases in cost and likely loss of authors who don't want to comply with new data sharing requirements.

Publishers – Supporting Data Sharing

- 1) Jobs
 - a) Ensure consistent metadata for true findability
 - b) Provide new jobs for Data Stewards
 - c) Provide education of value of data sharing for authors

- d) Offer incentives (badges, awards, etc.) to encourage data sharing
- e) Offer guidance on locating and using repositories (and possibly infrastructure)
- 2) Gains
 - a) Promotes **sound science**
 - b) Supports **compliance with funder** mandates (UK/EU/NIH)
 - c) Results in more **robust** papers
 - d) Allows for **faster** application of data to new experiments
 - e) Provides a **closer connection/linkage** of data with authors
 - f) Retains/attracts **authors** by providing infrastructure in research/publishing workflow
 - g) Improves **journal impact** (not just Impact Factor, but scientific impact)
- 3) Pains
 - a) Adds extra work for authors, reviewers, editors, and journal staff
 - b) Reduces revenue (increase costs, loss of authors)
 - c) Loss of editors and reviewers due to increasing workloads
 - d) Increases the number of policies that must be followed
 - e) Extends the turnaround time for reviews/decisions
 - f) Supports and maintains linkage between articles, data products, etc.